

Supporting text: Geological setting of the Triassic-Jurassic Boundary in the UK.

Paleoenvironment

This study examined the uppermost Triassic (Rhaetian) and lowest Jurassic (Hettangian) rocks at three sites in the UK. The Rhaetian Stage is represented by the Penarth Group, which is subdivided into the Westbury Formation and the overlying Lilstock Formation. Two members are recognized within the Lilstock Formation: the Cotham and Langport members. The Blue Lias Formation overlies the Penarth Group, and includes the base of the Jurassic System in its lower few meters (Hesselbo et al. 2004, Warrington 2008). The Hettangian part is subdivided into four ammonite biozones, comprising in ascending order: the Pre-Planorbis Zone, Planorbis Zone, Liasicus Zone and Angulata Zone (Warrington 2008) (Fig. 1).

The Westbury Formation is composed of an upward-coarsening marine succession. The lower part was deposited in deeper water below the wave base whilst the uppermost part records a shallower, prograding shoreface (Hesselbo et al. 2004, Warrington 2008). This shallowing trend continues into the overlying Cotham Member of the Lilstock Formation (Swift 1999, Wignall and Bond 2008) and culminates in subaerial exposure of these nearshore, peritidal sediments, indicating as a regionally-extensive, dessication-cracked surface (Hesselbo et al. 2004, Simms and Jeram 2007). This horizon is immediately overlain by transgressive, shallow marine rocks of the upper Cotham Member that represent a coastal environment and which record a negative excursion in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ (Hesselbo et al. 2004, Jaraula et al. 2013). The overlying Langport Member records deposition in a shallow lagoonal setting in a broad and shallow seaway (Hesselbo et al. 2004, Warrington 2008). The base of the Blue Lias Formation marks a

phase of rapid deepening, and the formation records deposition in an offshore, shelf setting (Swift 1999, Warrington 2008). Laminated organic-rich shales, which were deposited in an oxygen-restricted environment, occur at several levels in the lowermost beds of the formation (Hallam 1995, Hallam 1997, Wignall and Bond 2008). The basal transgressive succession of the Blue Lias Formation records a second and more prolonged negative excursion in $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$, which has been termed the ‘main isotope excursion event,’ and is considered to be distinct from the ‘initial isotope excursion’ of the Cotham Member (Hesselbo et al. 2002, Wignall and Bond 2008).

Extinction event and Triassic/Jurassic Boundary

The Westbury Formation records pre-extinction marine communities with high diversity and evenness (Mander et al. 2008). Species turnover, disappearance, and extinction occurred within the lower Lilstock Formation, below the negative isotope excursion (Hesselbo et al. 2004, Mander et al. 2008), and may have happened in a relatively short period of time [~40 kyr, (Ruhl et al. 2011)] (Fig. 1). Relatively low diversity communities (Mander et al. 2008), possibly reflecting harsh environmental conditions in lagoons of fluctuating salinity, are recorded to the top of the Lilstock Formation (Hesselbo et al. 2004). A significant marine transgression, and shift to offshore, shelf settings, marks the base of the overlying Blue Lias Formation. The post-extinction recovery of these shelf ecosystems has been well documented in both trace fossils (Barras and Twitchett 2007, Twitchett and Barras 2004) and body fossils (Mander et al. 2008, Pugh et al. 2014) and was complete by the Angulata Zone of the late Hettangian.

The TJB is defined by the first appearance of the ammonite species *Psiloceras spelae* in the GSSP section, Austria (Hillebrandt et al. 2007); despite this, *P. spelae* does not occur in the

UK, possibly due to the very short duration of this zone (Ruhl et al. 2010). As such, locally the TJB is instead defined by the first appearance of the pollen taxon *Cerebropollenites thiergartii*, which co-occurs with *P. spelae* in Austria (Bonis et al. 2010, Hillebrandt et al. 2007). The local TJB thus lies below the first ammonite, *P. erugatum*, in the Pre-Planorbis Zone of the Blue Lias Formation (Fig. 1 and Supplementary Figure 1). At St. Audrie's Bay, the TJB is placed at the top of Bed 6 or in the basal part of Bed 7 (see Steinthorsdottir et al. 2011); at Pinhay Bay, the TJB lies at the top of the bed (H25)(Weedon et al. 2017); whilst at Larne, the TJB is located in bed 22b (see Simms and Jeram 2007, Steinthorsdottir et al. 2011). The Pinhay Bay section does not record the initial carbon isotope excursion (CIE), because the Cotham Member is not exposed there, but the initial CIE is recorded at St. Audrie's Bay (in Bed 3 of the Cotham Member) (see Hesselbo et al. 2004, Warrington 2008) and at Larne (Bed 9 of the Cotham Member) (see Simms and Jeram 2007) (Supplementary Figure 1).

References

- Barras, C. G., and R. J. Twitchett. 2007. Response of the marine infauna to Triassic-Jurassic environmental change: Ichnological data from southern England. *Palaeogeography Palaeoclimatology Palaeoecology* 244(1-4):223-241.
- Bonis, N. R., M. Ruhl, and W. M. Kurschner. 2010. Milankovitch-scale palynological turnover across the Triassic-Jurassic transition at St. Audrie's Bay, SW UK. *Journal of the Geological Society* 167(5):877-888.
- Hallam, A. 1995. Oxygen-restricted facies of the basal Jurassic of North West Europe. *Historical Biology* 10:247-257.
- Hallam, A. 1997. Estimates of the amount and rate of sea-level change across the Rhaetian-Hettangian and Pliensbachian-Toarcian boundaries. *Journal of the Geological Society* (154):773-779.
- Hesselbo, S. P., S. A. Robinson, and F. Surlyk. 2004. Sea-level change and facies development across potential Triassic-Jurassic boundary horizons, SW Britain. *Journal of the Geological Society* 161:365-379.
- Hesselbo, S. P., S. A. Robinson, F. Surlyk, and S. Piasecki. 2002. Terrestrial and marine extinction at the Triassic-Jurassic boundary synchronized with major carbon-cycle perturbation: a link to initiation of massive volcanism? . *Geology* 30: 251-254.

- Hillebrandt, A. V., L. Krystyn, and W. M. Kueschner. 2007. A candidate GSSP for the base of the Jurassic in the Northern Calcareous Alps (Kuhjoch section; Karwendel Mountains, Tyrol, Austria). *International Subcommission on Jurassic Stratigraphy Newsletter* 34(1):2-20.
- Jaraula, C. M. B., K. Grice, R. J. Twitchett, M. E. Böttcher, P. LeMetayer, A. G. Dastidar, and L. F. Opazo. 2013. Elevated pCO₂ leading to Late Triassic extinction, persistent photic zone euxinia, and rising sea levels. *Geology* 41(9):955-958.
- Mander, L., R. J. Twitchett, and M. J. Benton. 2008. Palaeoecology of the Late Triassic extinction event in the SW UK. *Journal of the Geological Society* 165:319-332.
- Pugh, A. C., S. Danise, J. R. Brown, and R. J. Twitchett. 2014. Benthic ecosystem dynamics following the Late Triassic mass extinction event: Palaeoecology of the blue lias formation, Lyme Regis, UK. *Geoscience in South-West England* 13(3):255-266.
- Ruhl, M., N. R. Bonis, G. J. Reichart, J. S. S. Damste, and W. M. Kueschner. 2011. Atmospheric Carbon Injection Linked to End-Triassic Mass Extinction. *Science* 333(6041):430-434.
- Ruhl, M., M. H. L. Deenen, H. A. Abels, N. R. Bonis, W. Krijgsman, and W. M. Kueschner. 2010. Astronomical constraints on the duration of the early Jurassic Hettangian stage and recovery rates following the end-Triassic mass extinction (St Audrie's Bay/East Quantoxhead, UK). *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 295(1-2):262-276.
- Simms, M. J., and A. J. Jeram. 2007. Waterloo Bay, Larne, Northern Ireland: A potential Global Stratotype Section and Point (GSSP) for the base of the Jurassic System. *Newsletter of the International Subcommission on Jurassic Stratigraphy* (34):50-68.
- Steinhorsdottir, M., A. J. Jeram, and J. C. McElwain. 2011. Extremely elevated CO₂ concentrations at the Triassic/Jurassic boundary. *Palaeogeography Palaeoclimatology Palaeoecology* 308(3-4):418-432.
- Swift, A. 1999. Stratigraphy (Including Biostratigraphy). Pp. 15-37. *In* A. Swift, and D. M. Martill, eds. *Fossil of the Rhaetian Penarth Group*. The Paleontological Association, London.
- Twitchett, R. J., and C. G. Barras. 2004. Trace fossils in the aftermath of mass extinction events.
- Warrington, G., Cope J.C.W., and Ivimey-Cook, H.C., 2008. . 2008. The St Audrie's Bay – Doniford Bay section, Somerset, England: updated proposal for a candidate Global Stratotype Section and Point for the base of the Hettangian Stage, and of the Jurassic System. *International Subcommission on Jurassic Stratigraphy Newsletter* (35):1-74.
- Weedon, G., H. Jenkyns, and K. Page. 2017. Combined sea-level and climate controls on limestone formation, hiatuses and ammonite preservation in the Blue Lias Formation, South Britain (uppermost Triassic – Lower Jurassic). *Geological Magazine*:1-33.
- Wignall, P. B., and D. P. G. Bond. 2008. The end-Triassic and Early Jurassic mass extinction records in the British Isles. *Proceedings of the Geologists Association* 119:73-84.

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#Null Model, R code

#Charge the Null Model function
#####

dpbd=read.table("data.csv", header=TRUE, sep=",")

null.model<-function(data,it){

OUT<-NULL
for(t in 1:it){

M<-ifelse(data!=0,1,0)
Random.matrix<-matrix(0,nc=ncol(data),nr=nrow(data))
for(i in 1:nrow(data)){
index<-which(M[i,]==1)
samp<-sample(data[i,index],length(index),replace=FALSE)
Random.matrix[i,index]<-samp
}
out<-as.vector(apply(Random.matrix,2,mean))
OUT<-cbind(OUT,out)
}
obs<-as.vector(apply(data,2,mean))
esp.N.it<-as.vector(apply(OUT,1,mean))
return(list(res=cbind(obs,esp.N.it),iter=OUT))
}

#Run the Null Model
#####
d=read.table("data.csv", header=TRUE, sep=",")
pb=as.matrix(dpbd)
NM <-null.model(pb,10000)
pbiter= (t(NM$iter))
pbiter=write.csv(pbiter, file="pbiter.csv")

#####

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